

FUNDAMENTALS AND PRINCIPLES OF SIDDHAR VASI YOGAM (YOGA KARPAM): A LITERATURE REVIEW

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ABSTRACT

Siddhar Yoga Maruthuvam is a pivotal wing of Siddha Medical Science that reckons with study of Kaya Karpam, Yoga adhanams, Mudhirai and Dhiyaanam. Vāciyōkam is one of the 64 kinds of Yogam in Siddha System. It is a technical art of harmonizing and equilibrizing the three bodies – gross body (Sthoola Sareeram), subtle body (Sukhchuma Sareeram) and causal body (Karana Sareeram). This is attained through the yogam practices such as Asana, Pranayama, Mudra and Bandha. Vasi Yogam aims at bringing the different bodily functions into perfect coordination in physical, mental and emotions level. It is one of the Yogic maneuvers that deal with the way to attain self realisation, enlightenment and true consciousness. Among the ten vital forces, Prana travels along the three bodies in different forms.

Prana Vaayu in gross body, engaged in respiration varies from Prana vaayu flowing inside subtle body. The energy flow of Vital force (Prana Vaayu) in subtle body is known as Vaasi. Thus Vāciyōkam is a methodology to regulate the Vasi inside gross and subtle bodies to attain enlightenment. Through practice of Vasi Yogam, awareness develops on interrelation between the emotional, mental and Physical levels which leads to profound understanding of subtle areas (metaphysical theory) of existence. This study will explore the attainment of essence of molecular biological science by Siddhars through Vasi Yogam Practice.

KEYWORDS: Vasi Yogam, Yogic Breathing, Subtle breath, Enlightenment, Rejuvenation, Siddhar Yogic maneuver.

INTRODUCTION

Siddha system is a holistic indigenous Medical Science of great antiquity. Siddhar Yoga Maruthuvam is a pivotal wing of Siddha Medical Science that reckons with study of Kaya Karpam, Yoga adhanams, Mudhirai and Dhiyaanam. *Vāciyōkam* is one of the 64 kinds of Yogam in Siddha System. It is a technical art of harmonizing and equilibrizing the three bodies - gross body (Sthoola Sareeram), subtle body (Sukhchuma Sareeram) and causal body (Karana Sareeram). This is attained through the yogam practices such as Asana, Pranayama, Mudra and Bandha. Vasi Yogam aims at bringing the different bodily functions into perfect coordination in physical, mental and emotions level.

It is one of the Yogic maneuvers that deal with the way to attain self realisation, enlightenment and true consciousness. For ideal functioning of human, Ten vital forces (Dhasa vaayus) namely Pranana, Abhana, Uthana, Samana, Viyana, Naaga, Koorma, Kirugara, Dhevadhathana and Dhananjeyana must be channelized along the pathway of ten vital energy channels (Dhasa Naadi). Ten vital forces and ten vital energy channels are combined to conduct the physiological functions of human body. Among these ten essential channels, Idagalai, Pingalai and Suzhumunai are the significant channels that carry vasi throughout body. Among these ten vital forces, Pranana travels along the three bodies in different forms. Prana Vaayu in gross body, engaged in respiration varies from Prana vaayu flowing inside subtle body. The energy flow of Vital force (Prana Vaayu) in subtle body is known as Vaasi. Thus *Vāciyōkam* is a methodology to regulate the Vasi inside gross and subtle bodies to attain enlightenment. *Vāciyōkam* practice is perceived from various Siddha Literatures. Different methodologies have been followed by various Siddhars. Distinct perspectives about *Vāciyōkam* are explored and collated in this study.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. STUDY DESIGN

Descriptive study

B. STUDY TYPE

Literature Review

C. STUDY PERIOD

4 Months

D. STUDY PLACE

- Library of Government Siddha Medical College, Palayamkottai, Tirunelveli
- Library of National Institute of Siddha Tambaram Sanitorium.
- Doctor Ambedkar Central library of Indian Medicine, Chennai.
- The Anna Centenary Library, Kotturpuram, Chennai
- Library of ATSVS College, Munchirai.

E. SOURCES OF LITERATURE

- Siddha Classical Text books available in Libraries
- Standard Search Engines and online repositories
- Articles, Journals

F. METHODOLOGY

- Identifying the key search terms
- Searching of literatures
- Analyzing the literatures
- Compilation and Writing the Literature
- Documentation and Submission of Project report.

DATA COLLECTION

- Literature evidences on Siddhar Vasi Yogam will be cumulated from the Library. The collected data will be collated and documented accordingly.

EXPECTED OUTCOME

- Through this study, a compendium on fundamentals and principles of Siddhar Vasi Yogam practice will be accomplished.
- An insight into Vasi Yogam practice will be furnished for future extensive researches and studies.

Widespread of Vasi Yogam concepts in various Siddha literatures can be acknowledged.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The essence of *Vāciyōkam* has been cited in Siddha Literatures written by various Siddhars.

“Vēṇumaṭā citamparattai pārkkaveṇṇrāl

tōnumatā civayōkam vāci yōkam”

- *Tēraiya civapūjā viti verse 69*

“Nilaiyāna civayōka niṭṭaiyālum

vārappā pirāṇāyam vāci yōkam”

- *Tēraiya civapūjā viti verse 74*

“Oḷipeṛa vāci yōkam mūṭṭiṇāl civayō kantāṇ

oḷipeṛa pūra ṇattai mēviṇā lavarkkē

citti vaḷipaṭa vātam pārṭtu

maṇaṅkeṭa alaiya vēṇṭām

cuḷimuṇai perṛōrk kallāl

turiyamuṅ kiṭaiyā teṇṇē”

-*Pōkar cōṭaca cūttiram verse 43*

1.1 SYNONYMS

Vasi Yogam Methodology is mentioned in various Siddha classical Literatures with different terminologies. The analogous terminologies to *Vāci yōkam* explored in Siddha texts can be interpreted with their Literature verses.

S.NO	SYNONYMS	LITERATURE VERSE	LITERATURE REFERENCE
1.	<i>Cuḷumuṇai yōkam</i>	<i>“Cuḷumuṇai yōkañ catur nālu cāman toṭucaramām vaḷiyum pēriṇpa matuvāri yuṇṭu vaṇamatuvāyc cuḷiyāmal kālaiyu mālaiyu mucchi kaṇṭattilum aḷiyāp pataviyil vācikkoṇṭu.....”</i>	<i>Tiruvaḷḷuva nāyanār ṇāṇaveṭṭiyāṇ 1500</i>
2.	<i>Pirāṇa yōkam</i>	<i>“Kānappā vāciyenra eḷuttai nanrāy kaṇṭākkāl kāyacitti kāna vēṇum pēṇappā uṇmaṇatai yaṛiyāmarrāṇpēroḷiyāy niṛpatuvē pirāṇa yōkam”</i>	<i>Cuntarāṇantar meyṇāṇa curukkam16</i>
3.	<i>Makārāja yōkam</i>	<i>“Nāṭiṭu miṇikkēḷ makārāja yōkam nāṭṭuvēṇ vairākya ṇāṇam naṭattaiyeṇ raiya vāciyō kattil”</i>	<i>Pulattiyar kaṛṇam 300</i>
4.	<i>Meyṇāṇa yōkam</i>	<i>Āmētāṇ kaṇṭatellām viḷaiyāṭṭenru arintu koḷvāy puttiraṇē yaṛivuḷḷōṇē nāmētāṇ collukira māṛkkantaṇṇai naṇmaiyaṭa neyarintu naṭakkavēṇum vāmēṇi vāciyenra puraviyēri makattāṇa cuḷinaiparri yaṛivircērttu tāmētā ṇavvarivir cōkkininru cantatamu meyṇāṇa yōkampārē.</i>	<i>Viḷaiyāṭṭu cittar ṇāṇa cūttiram</i>
5.	<i>Pañca kaṇa tīṭcai</i>	<i>Puṇitamutaṇ tāṇiruntu pūcai paṇṇi poṛkamala vucciyiṇ mēḷ maṇatai vaṭṭu iṇita mutaṇ akāra meṇṛāl vāciyāccu yōka meṇra vāciyilē iṇṇam</i>	<i>Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti</i>

		<i>vaittu karuvi karanamāṇa civacatti vālai kaṇṇāṇa pūraṇamum nāluṅ kūṭṭi maṇikaraṇa māṇatoru aintum maintā makattāṇa paṅcakaṇa tīṭṭaiyāccē verse 45</i>	
6.	<i>Dhasa theetchai</i>	<i>Ēcciṭṭār civa tīkṣai pattaiyun tāṅ itamāka marait tallō vāci yenrum coṇṇār mācciṭṭu kuḷikai yenrār kāya citti yenrār māykai pōl oḷittallō māyañ ceytār (verse 363)</i>	<i>Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti</i>
7.	<i>Vāci tāraṇai</i>	<i>Nōkkaṭā ātāram paṇireṇṭumpārttu uṇmaiyaṭaṅ tamarvācaṅ kuḷḷēvāci tākkaṭā rēcakamāy kaṅṭampāyūm caktiyiṭai pāyāmar piṅkalaikkērēci vākkaṭā mēlvācal pūṭṭiviṭṭāl makattāṇa poriyatuvum pūtātayyā nākkaṭā vācitā raṇaiyumāccu nalamāṇa cuḷimuṇaiyil nāṇinillē verse 1064</i>	<i>Akattiyar caumiya cākaram 1200</i>
8.	<i>Akāra ukāra tīṭṭai</i>	<i>Tāṇenra ātāra mūlam pārkkac cātakattaic collukirēṅ nanrāyḱ kēlu kōmenra kuruvuruḷā lakāra tīṭṭai koṅṭapiṅpu ukāra maṭācatti tīṭṭai</i>	<i>Apūrvam akattiyar maruttuvam</i>

6.2 DEFINITION

VASI

Subtle breath that channelizes and circulates through the subtle energy channels of subtle body is called *Vāci*. The manipulation of this subtle breath is essential for initiating the attainment of enlightenment.

S.NO	VASI	LITERATURE REFERENCE
1.	<i>Vāci</i> is located at 1 inch below navel (Naabi)/Umbilical region in crescent shape. “ <i>Vitturukkum vāciyatu yenkēyenrāl uyyappā nāpiyiṅkī lōraṅkulattukkappāl utittapirai pōlirukkum paiyiṅcōti ayyappā cāṇaraitāṅ kuḷalaippatti appaṅē toṅkumaṭā aṭavāyppārē</i> ”	<i>Akattiyar vāta kāviyam 1000</i>
2.	<i>Vāci</i> is a thermal energy residing in the <i>Mūlatāram</i> Region	<i>Akattiyar vāta caumiyam 1200</i>
3.	<i>Vāci</i> is a form of ray that arises in <i>Cuḷumuṇai</i> on controlling 5 special senses	<i>Tiruvalluva nāyaṅār ṅāṇaveṭṭiyāṅ 1500</i>
4.	<i>Vāci</i> is the energized vital force (<i>Pirāṅā Vāyu</i>) that travels from <i>Mūlatāram</i> to <i>Ākkinai</i> .	<i>Tiruvalluva nāyaṅār ṅāṇaveṭṭiyāṅ 1500</i>
5.	The union of thermal energy (<i>Mūla Akṇi</i>) residing in <i>Mūlatāram</i> & energized <i>Pirāṅā Vāyu</i> (Vital force) is called as <i>Vāci</i> “ <i>Aṭuttuṇilai kāttatiṅāl maintāmaintā ātāra mulamatāl aṭukkuttōṇum naṭuttiramāy niṅṅramaṇai taṅṅaiappōrri nātānta naṭaṇamattai nāṭippārttu Toṭuttuṇinra vāciyilē aṭuttukkattut turuvamenra puruvamataṅ cuḷiyaippārtāl kaṭuttuṇinra kālaṇavaṅ vilakip pōvāṅ karuṇaivaḷar</i> ”	<i>Akattiyar pūraṇa kāviyam 1000</i>

	<i>vāciyilē karuttāy nīllē</i>	
6.	<i>Vāci</i> is formed by union of revamped <i>Pirāṇā Vāyu</i> and <i>Mūla Akṣi</i> (Thermal energy) <i>“Kāṇavē ṁkārām piratāṇam tāṇ karuvāṇa ātāram mūla pīṭam tōṇavē mūlameṇṇra ātārattil tulaṅki niṇṇra āviyaṭā vāciyāccu pēṇavē āviyeṇṇra vāciyēri perukiniṇṇra ātāram kaṭantappālē pūṇavē ravimatiyum cuṭaril ceṇṇru puttiyuṭaṇ pūraṇamāy tīpam pare”</i>	<i>Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti</i>
7.	<i>Vāci</i> is revamped form of <i>Pirāṇāṇ</i> that moves across 9 orifices of body and helps to control 21,600 Suvasam (breath) inside our body.	<i>Taṇvantiri karukkaṭai nikaṇṭu</i>
8.	<i>Vāci</i> is energized Prana Vayu which is channelized across Idakalai, Pingalai and <i>Cuḷumuṇai</i> Naadis (energy channels) through inter relation with mid mystic centers (aadharam).	T.V.Sambasivampillai Dictionary Volume - 5
9.	Vasi is energized Prana which is subtle and fine like a thin ray. When Prana attains subtle frequency, Vasi arises	<i>Akattiyar vāci cūttiram 10</i>

VASI YOGAM

Vasi Yogam can be elaborated as the path of Enlightenment by channelizing and regulating the subtle breath (Vasi) at the site of glabella aiming to open the “Third Eye” in the state of Transcendence.

According to *Pulattiyar karpam 300*, *Vāciyōkam* is defined as the yogic technique through which Vasi travels along *Cuḷumuṇai* Naadi pathway towards glabella (Midpoint of eye brows).

Cuppiramaṇiyar ṇāṇam 200 defines *Vāciyōkam* as union of three Regions (Mandalams) namely Agni Mandalam, Suriya Mandalam, and Chandhira Mandalam which should be practiced for 5 years.

According to *Akattiyar vāta caumiyam 1200*, the union of three predominant Energy channels (Idakalai, Pingalai and *Cuḷumuṇai*) at their interrelated centre point through Vasi is known as *Vāciyōkam*. The Vaasi Energy from the physiopsychic centre Mooladharam is manipulated along the pathway of *Cuḷumuṇai* energy channel towards the glabella (Midpoint of eye brows) followed by concentration at glabella region uttering primordial chant “Vasi Vasi” for 108 times.

According to *Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti*, *Vāciyōkam* is the practice of Intrinsic pranayamam through Vasi for 1 Kadigai (24 minutes) duration. Agathiyar refers “Dhasa

Theetchai” as *Vāciyōkam* that involves the union of Agaram and Ugaram

“*Kūravē mūlattiḷ vāci koṇṭu*
kōḷi muṭṭai pōliruntu mukkoṇattiḷ
māravē iṭaiṇṇāy iraṇṭum oṭum
marroru cuḷimuṇaitāṇ makiḷntu kēḷē”

“*Cērappā akāramuṭaṇ ukāraṇ kūṭṭi*
cāmamuṭaṇ uruvētti niṇṇāyāṇāl
tērappā niṇṇa tiru vāciyālē nilaiyāṇa puruvamatil paṇ kāṇum
kārappā tīpamatai kamalak kaṇṇāl
kaṇṇarintu vāci yaṇāl uṇṇipapāru
cārappā vāciyaṇāl uṇṇip parka” verse -41

INTERPRETATION OF AGARAM, UGARAM AND MAGARAM

The sacred syllable Om is the primordial sound from which all other sounds and phonetic creations emerge. The utterance of Om, consisting of the three letters A, U, and M, covers the whole process of articulation. It is like the sound of a gong that gradually tapers to a point and merges in silence. This syllable Om is anecdotally reported to cause a harmonization of mental state and attainment of true consciousness and enlightenment.

This syllable is the combination of three letters, namely, A, U, and M. Various Siddhars have interpreted these three syllables with multifaceted approach. It is the combination of three letters, namely, A, U, and M. “A” represents the physical plane (Gross body). “U” represents the mental and astral plane, (Subtle body). “M” represents Causal body.

In some other Literatures, “A” represents Agni Mandalam, “U” represents Sooriya Mandalam and “M” represents Chandhira Mandalam (3 Regions of body). Each Regions enholds two psychophysical centres respectively. Agni Mandalam encompasses centers of Mooladharam and Suvaadhittanam. Sooriya Mandalam encompasses centers of Manipooragam and Anagadham. Chandhira Mandalam encompasses centers of Visudhi and Aakinai.

Other school of thought interprets Agaram, Ugaram and Magaram with the three predominant vital energies. Thus “A” represents Pingalai, “U” represents Idagalai and “M” represents *Culumunai*.

Āmappā cōṭacattiṅ kalaiyullāki
aruḷ tīpam nōkkutarḱu tiravukōl tāṅ
ōmappā ukarantāṅ miṅ pōl miṅṅa
uru mūla nāṭiyilē muḷaṅki niṅkum
nāmappā akārantāṅ hirutayat tuḷḷē
nāṭiyē akkiṅi pōl piṅaiyē vicum
tāmappā makārattāṅ kaṅṅattullē
tayavāṅa mati kōṭi kāṅṅiyāmē.
Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti Verse 385

SCIENTIFIC SIGNIFICANCE OF OM SYLLABLE:

Om Syllable results in physiological alertness, and increased sensitivity to sensory transmission. It leads to increase in the cutaneous peripheral vascular resistance which is a sign of increased mental alertness.

It enables an increase in the synchronicity of cardiovascular rhythms and increase in baroflex sensitivity. It causes decrease in the heart and breath rates and reduces the skin resistance, suggesting a subtle change in the mental state.

During prolonged chanting of “Om”,

- ❖ Oxygen level within body increases and the level of carbon-dioxide and Lactic Acid decreases.
- ❖ The level of Neurotransmitters increases and energizes the movement of alpha, beta and delta waves of brain. The Endocrine secretions of brain such as Serotonin and Dopamine also peak high.
- ❖ Vasi Yogam practice simulates two special hormones
1. Serotonin 2. Melatonin. These two hormones ultimately stabilizes all the working systems in our body. They also help in experiencing the spiritual feeling in our body.
- ❖ Serotonin (Neural controller of brathing) is a powerful modulator of respiratory network that regulates synaptic and intrinsic properties of respiratory neurons.
- ❖ Increased Dopamine levels in the brain’s striatum basal ganglia enhances focus and concentration.

RESEVOIRS OF VASI

According to *Arunācala kuru nijānanta pōtam*, Vasi resides in 5 locations.

- ❖ Crown of Head (Sahasram)
- ❖ Occiput region (Pidari)
- ❖ Glabella (Naasi munai)
- ❖ Chest region (Nenju)
- ❖ Coccyx region (Moolam)

TIME AND DURATION

The ideal time and duration to practice *Vāciyōkam* is discussed in different Literatures. The appropriate time of *Vāciyōkam* practice and its duration varies from the school of thoughts of each Siddhar. Regular practice of *Vāciyōkam* in optimal time is the key to maximize the benefits from it by concentrating upon natural rhythms and energy cycles of body. This practice leads to increased energy levels and improved spiritual well being by enabling the practitioner to connect more deeply with their inner self.

S.NO	TIME AND DURATION	LITERATURE REFERENCE
1.	Vasi Yogam is practiced for 1 Kadigai (24 minutes) duration upon doing Pooragam, Kambagam, Iresagam internally [intrinsic pranayamam]. Vasi energizes on 1 year practice of this Yogam. It moves upwards on 3 Years practice. Vasi Yogam is performed for 1 Saamam [3 hours] Gradually, it is done for 25 kadaigai (10 hours) duration in early morning time. After continuous practice of 2 years, it is practiced for 4 Saamam (12 hours) thrice a day. “ <i>Mūṭṭiyē murāiyākac ceytu patamāy uṭkoṇṭu kālaitaṇil collak kēlu māṭṭiyāy vāciyiṇāl culiyilēri pārappā jāmamatuṇṇu nālu jāmam kōṭiyilē yirukku mappō valiyiṇattai kaṇṭu koṇṭu tirikālam vācikoṇṭu nāṭṭamuṭaṇ ūti yaruḷ peruvāyappā nāṇ conṇēṇ pulattiyāṇē unakkāyt tāṇē.</i> ”	<i>Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti</i>
2.	It should be performed for 17 Naazhigai. On prolonged practice of <i>Vāciyōkam</i> for 10 years with duration about 20 Naazhigai, aids to attain Kaya Siddhi.	<i>Akattiyar vāta kāviyam 1000</i>
4.	This methodology should be practiced in morning and evening time before food for 1 Mookurtam (1 hour 30 minutes) a day for 3 years continuously.	<i>Kākapujaṅṅar perunūl kāviyam 1000</i>
5.	It is performed in early morning at dawn time, for 25 Kadigai. By verses 832, It is practiced in early morning for 4 Saamam during morning, afternoon & evening (thrice a day) for 3 years. Prior practice of Pranayamam for about 10 months to 3 years is essential to perform Vasi Yogam. The ideal month to practice Vasi Yogam is Iypasi. It is preferred to avoid this practice during Chithirai month, as this leads to rapid manipulation of fire residing in Mooladharm (Moola Agni)	<i>Tiruvalluva nāyaṅār ṅāṇaveṭṭiyāṅ 1500</i>

PROCEDURE

Siddhars manifest the essential role of Guru, whose spiritual intellect paves way to realize the inherent true consciousness. They emphasize to perform Vasi Yogam only under the guidance of Guru.

“*kāṇalāṅ kuruvaik kaṇṭu kaḷikkalā molikka lāmē.*”

Oḷipera vāci yōkam

mūṭṭiṇāl civayō kantāṇ

oḷipera pūra ṇattai

mēviṇā lavarkkē citti
valīpaṭa vātam pārṭtu
maṇaṅkeṭa alaiya vēṇṭām
cuḷimuṇai perṛōrk kallāl
turiyamuṅ kiṭaiyā teṇṇē.”

- *Pōkar cōṭaca cūttiram Verse 43*

PREMONITORY PREPARATIONS

- ❖ The Siddha treatise *Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti* mentions to manipulate Vasi only after coordinating the functioning of Ten vital forces (Dhasa vaayus) at the site of Coccyx (Mooladharam)
- ❖ Other Siddha Literature *Tiruvalluva nāyaṅār ṅāṇaveṭṭiyān 1500* emphasizes to do external pranayamam to constrain 10 Vaayus together at the region of Coccyx (Mooladharam).

METHODOLOGY

Various methodologies for the practice of Vasi Yogam have been enumerated by our Siddhars in their classical Literatures. The accomplishment of the essence of Vasi Yogam is enabled through the strategies of

- ❖ Utterance of Primordial Sounds (Mandhiram)
- ❖ Practice of Aadhanam and Bandhams
- ❖ Practice of Mudras
- ❖ Manipulation along Physiopsychic centers (Aadharams)

- ❖ Maneuvering through Subtle energy channels (Naadi pathways)
- ❖ Coalescence of 3 Regions (*Maṅṭalam*)
- ❖ Subtle Pranayamam practice (Subtle Inhalation, Retention and Exhalation (Pooragam, Kumbagam, Iresagam)
- ❖ Consumption of Kaya Karpam

SINGASANAM

Bound Angle pose
Baddha Konasana
Bhadrasana

PATHIRASANAM

PADMASANAM

S.NO	MEHODOLOGY	LITERATURE REFERENCE
1.	<p>Vasi residing in Mooladharam (Subtle energy plexes) is in the form of thermal energy. This is manipulated through Uvula (Annakku) inside throat and is regulated along the pathways of energy channels Idagalai and Pingalai by crossing 6 Aadharams (Subtle energy plexes) to reach glabella. Prolonged Vasi yogam practice leads to attainment of Siva Raja Yogam (the stage of transcendence).</p> <p>Agathiyar emphasizes to perform the manipulation of this Yogam through Aadharams (Subtle Energy Plexes). It is suggested that Vasi yogam must not be practiced through nostrils.</p> <p>By reciting the syllable “Vang” for 8 seconds, Vasi in Mooladharam subtle energy plexes is activated to ascend upwards and channelize through the energy channel Idakalai and it is followed by chant of sound “Sing” for 8 seconds during upward manipulation of Vasi to reach the Aagainai. The ascended Vasi constricts and seals the nine orifices of body (Nava tuvāram) and subsides in <i>Culumunai</i> energy channel.</p> <p>In higher form of Vasi yogam, initially Vasi is channelized through the energy channel Idakalai to reach glabella and it is concentrated for a period of 4 Saamam (12 hours). This should be practised regularly for 10 Months to 3 Years.</p> <p>“<i>Mūṭṭiyē muraiyākac ceytu patamāy uṭṭoṅṭu kālāitaṅṅil collak kēḷu māṭṭiṭāy vāciyiṅṅāl cuḷiyilēri pārappā jāmamatumum nālu jāmam kōṭiyilē yirukku mappō vaḷiyiṅṅattai kaṅṭu koṅṭu tirikālam vācikoṅṭu nāṭṭamuṅṅaṅ ūti yaruḷ peruvāyappā</i>”</p>	<p><i>Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti</i></p>

	<p><i>nāṅ conṇēṅ pulattiyaṅē uṅakkāyt tāṅē.</i>” Verse -86</p> <p>Then Vasi is manipulated by chant of syllable “Ang” by practice of Irasagam, Pooragam and Kumbagam along the <i>Culumuṅai</i> energy channel. This is performed for about 3 years in the stage of Dhuriyaatheetham. After 3 years, subtle thermal energy arises at Aaginai site. To descend Vasi, it has to be manipulated by subtle energy plexes (Aadharam).</p>	
2.	<p>Vasi at Mooladharam (subtle energy plexes / psychophysical centre) is maneuvered along the Lunar energy channel (Idagalai) by chant of the primordial syllable ‘Ongaram’ (Om). It reaches glabella Region, within 24 minutes. (1 Nazhigai). This should be practiced by facing towards North direction and after practicing for 6 hours (15 Naazhigai) duration, the same procedure must be repeated by facing towards South direction.</p> <p>This Vasi yogam has to be practiced for 10 years Vasi has to be manipulated along Lunar energy channel (Idagalai). Minimum of 5 years practice of Vasi yogam is essential for the Yogic rejuvenation as disease preventing method.</p>	<i>Akattiyar vāta kāviyam 1000</i>
3.	<p>Vasi yogam is manipulated through movement of Vasi. Vasi is driven upwards from Mooladharam towards centre of brow (Glabella) for one minute (Pooragam) along the <i>Culumuṅai</i> energy channel. It is retended at Glabella (Kumbagam) for 2 minutes. Then it is manipulated downwards again towards Mooladharam from Glabella within 10 – 20 seconds (Iresagam). Thus Vasi is manaeuvered across Agni Mandalam (Agaaram), Sooriya Mandalam (Ugaaram) and Chandhra Mandalam (Magaaram).</p>	<i>Rāmatēvar civayōkam 40</i>
4.	<p>Vasi yoga meditation is performed along with 6 mudras (psychic hand gestures) namely</p> <p><i>Āvārakaṅ muttirai, Yōṅi muttirai, Tiruviṅi muttirai, Cōpiṅi muttirai, Mōkiṅi muttirai and Tāvaṅa muttirai</i></p> <p>In 8 stages of Pranayamam, Vasi is accomplished at the 4th stage.</p> <p>The Yogic posture of Gomukhasanam is manifested for the practice of Vasi Yogam. Middle finger and ring finger are used to apply pressure over the root of tongue. Tip of Tongue must touch Uvula (Unnaaku).</p> <p>Vasi yogam is manipulated thrice a day to unite the midpoint joining Idagalai, Pingalai and <i>Culumuṅai</i> energy channels by constant chant of syllable (mandhiram) “Om Reeng Sivaya Vasi”.</p> <p>The union of Idakalai, Pingalai, <i>Culumuṅai</i> end point through Vasi is known as Vasi yogam.</p>	<i>Akattiyar vāta caumiyam 1200</i>

	The advanced form of Vasi yogam, (Siva yogam) is performed by inhaling (Poorakam) with chant of ‘Om Reeng’ for 8 times. By chanting, Vasi ascends to uvula where it is retained (Kumbagam) for about 16 Māttirai duration by chanting ‘Om Reeng Ang’. Then it directed to <i>Cuḷumunai</i> Savu beejam (32 Māttirai) & Nir beejam (64 Māttirai) by chanting “Vasi Vaa Om”.	
5.	Vasi Yogam is the subtle breath manipulation to retain the futile breath into our body again.	<i>Kākapujaṅṭar ñāṅam 80</i>
6.	The coalescence of 3 Regions (Mandalam) through Vasi manipulation along the Idagalai and Pingalai channels by permeating into six mystic centers (Aadharams) to reach Glabella is the ideal procedure for the practice of Vasi Yogam. Immortality is attained after 13 years practise of this Yogic practice.	<i>Cuppiramaṅṅiyar ñāṅam 200</i>
7.	<p>The procedure of Vasi Yogam involves the utterance of chant (Mandhiram) “Vasi Vaa”. During this Yogic practice, both eyes should focus on Glabella region.</p> <p>Only after 3 years regular practice of Pranayamam, Vasi Yogam must be initiated.</p> <p>Vasi yogam is accomplished in 3 phases - Subtle exhalation (Iresagam), Subtle inhalation (Pooragam) and Subtle retention (Kumbagam).</p> <p>Vasi is manipulated from mystic center (Mooladharam) by performing subtle exhalation (Iresagam) with syllable “Vang”. After reaching the Anagadham site, it is further directed upwards by chant of syllable “Sing”.</p> <p>Then by chanting “Vasi Vasi Vaya Nama Vang” subtle breath is maneuvered from Uvula opening (Kanda Thuvaram) by performing subtle exhalation (Iresagam) and subtle retention (Kumbagam) of Vasi. It ascends to reach the Glabella (<i>Cuḷumunai</i>).</p> <p>During retention phase, Vasi has to be retained at each sites of Throat (Kandam), Chest (Marbu) and Mooladharam for 10 seconds.</p> <p>Vasi is descended by chanting the primordial syllable “Om”. This upward and downward manipulation of subtle breath (Vasi) in Vasi yogam should be practised for 3 years.</p>	<i>Tiruvalluva nāyaṅār ñāṅavettiyaṅ 1500</i>
8.	<p>Vasi is ascended through opening of vertebral column towards glabella.</p> <p>This yogic procedure is performed by manipulating the subtle breath across six physiopsychic centers (Aadharam) by uttering the syllables ‘Vang’ and ‘Sing’. At each physiopsychic center (aadharam), subtle breath is retained (Kumbagam).</p> <p>The primordial sound ‘Om’ is the basis of Vasi yogam. The subtle breath coalesces and connects three centre points of <i>Cuḷumunai</i> energy channel (upper Moolam, middle Moolam</p>	<i>Kākapujaṅṭar perunūl kāviyam 1000</i>

	and lower Moolam) during Vasi Yogam.	
9.	The initiation of subtle breath from base of Coocyx region (Mooladharam) has to be done to circulate along the Solar energy channel (Pingalai) intermediating through physiopsychic centers (Aadharam) to reach Glabella. Subtle inhalation (Pooragam) is performed along the Lunar energy channel (Idagalai) for 2 seconds. Subtle retention (Kumbagam) is performed along the <i>Cuḷumuṇai</i> energy channel for 4 seconds. Subtle exhalation (Iresagam) is done for 1 minute along Solar energy channel (Pingalai). Siddhar Bogar emphasizes to perform Vasi Yogam procedure in Waxing Phase of Moon (Valarpirai) in month of Maasi.	<i>Pōka muṇivar civayōka ṅāṇam 12</i>
10.	The Subtle breath that wavers across the routes of three energy channels Idagalai, Pingalai and <i>Cuḷumuṇai</i> is called “Ajabaa”.	<i>Pōkar muppu cūttira ṅāṇam</i>
11.	This Yogic Practice is proceeded with utterance of chant of “Vasi vaa” during manipulation of subtle breath across 6 Physiopsychic centers (Aadharams). This subtle breath has to be retained at each Aadharam for sometime.	<i>Tirumūlar karukkaṭai vaittiyam 600</i>
12.	The Yogic procedure is practiced through Uvula (Kanda Thuvaaram) for about 40 days. One year regular practice of Vasi Yogam is necessary for sophisticated manipulation of Vasi. This Classical Literature suggests to practice Vasi yogam along with consumption of Karum Kaiyaan (black variety of <i>Eclipta prostrata</i>) Karpam and Meni Karpam (<i>Acalypha indica</i>).	<i>Taṅvantiri karukkaṭai nikaṇṭu</i>
13.	Vasi Yogam is the yogic rejuvenation practice that involves maneuvering subtle breath along the subtle energy channel (<i>Cuḷumuṇai</i> pathway) through intermediate junctions of physiopsychic centers (6 Aadharams). <i>Vāci yeṅra yiṭakalaiyil pūraṇantāṅ reṅṭu varicaiyuḷḷa cuḷiṅaiyilē kumpakantāṅṅālu tēciyeṅra piṅkalaiyil rēcakannāṅṅoru cem'maiyuṭaṅ palaraṅaiyai yoṭṭuccantiraṅ vēciyeṅra murai am'māvāci toṭṭu nicamāka valarpiraiyirrākkippāru māciyeṅra pittanīr pāyāvaṅṅam matipāttuk kaṅṅālē ṅōkkuvāyē</i> -verse 1063	<i>Akattiyar caumiya cākaram 1200</i>
14.	Hold Vasi at glabella site and do exhalation (Iresagam) along <i>Suḷhumunai</i> . Then perform Nirbeeja Pranayamam to attain Vasi yogam. The subtle breath manipulation along the physiopsychic centers (Aadharams) leads to opening and activation of <i>Cuḷumuṇai</i> energy channel. The manifested Aasanams to perform Vasi yogam include Singaasanam, Pathirasanam and Pooraiyaasanam.	<i>Pōkar 7000</i>
15.	Vasi yogam is the upward manipulation of subtle breath towards Aakinai.	<i>Tēraiyaar civapūjā viti</i>

16.	The procedure of this Yogic technique involves kindling of subtle breath from Mooladhara mystic center towards glabella followed by performing subtle exhalation, inhalation and retention (Iresagam, Pooragam and Kumbagam)	<i>Kālānkinātar pūjā viti</i>
17.	Vasi evolves on union of Ugaaram and Omkaaram at the site of mystic center (Mooladharam). Subtle exhalation, inhalation and retention have to be performed to attain Vasi yogam.	<i>Rāmatēvar civayōkam 40 Rāmatēvar ñāṇakēcari</i>
18.	This Yogic technique is maneuvered from Mooladharam towards Aaginai by kindling the subtle breath. It has to be performed in posture of Padmasanam.	<i>Cīva vākkīyar yōkam</i>
19.	The subtle breath (Vasi) is directed from Mooladharam and is behelded in Umblical region with chant of ‘Vang’ and in chest region with chant of “Ang”. Subtle exhalation of subtle breath from Mooladharam is performed for 2 ½ Maathirai and Subtle inhalation for 1 ½ Maathirai is performed to reach Throat region. This opens the uvula.	<i>Maccamuṇi nāyaṇār tirumantiram</i>
20.	Vasi Yogam is performed by the practice of Subtle exhalation, inhalation and retention (Iresagam, Pooragam and Kumbagam) of Subtle breath (Vasi) internally to attain Vasi yogam. The consumption of Saathikkai Karpam (<i>Myristica fragrans</i>) is manifested during the vasi Yogam practice.	<i>Kōrakkar cantirarēkai 200</i>
21.	Subtle Inhalation, exhalation and retention of subtle breath along the <i>Cūlumuṇai</i> energy channel in ratio of 32:16:64 (Pooragam, Iresagam and Kumbagam. This subtle breath is manipulated to coalesce Agaaram and Ugaaram	<i>Pulattiyar karpam 300</i>

TECHNIQUES TO CHANNELIZE VASI:

RUBBING UVULA

Tip of Tongue is bent upwards to rub the uvula in fanning motion

“Nāviṇ nuṇiyai naṭuvē vicirīṭil

cīvaṇum aṅkē civaṇum uraiviṭam”

- *Tirumūlar tirumantiram* verse 803

UVULA COMPRESSION

Uvula must be compressed with Tip of Tongue

“Ukantuniṇru cuvācamvēli pōkāmal tāṇ

uttamaṇē tāṇirutta vakaiyaik kēlu.....

ūṇavē cuḷiṇaiyilē maṇinā vūṇṇi

ōtātu vācipū rakamān tāṇē”

- *Akattiyar caumiya cākaram* 1200 verse 1057,1058

PERFORMING MOOLA BANDHA

- According to *Akattiyar caumiya cākaram* 1200 verse 94, It is practiced in siddhasanam. Use heel of left foot to touch the pelvic floor and exert moderate pressure
- Draw a long breath and tighten the pelvic floor on beginning of exhalation.
- Contract anus to improve control of muscles in the pelvic diaphragm and concentrate to Mooladharam.

CONSUMPTION OF KAYA KARPAM

S.NO	KAYA KARPAM	LITERATURE REFERENCE
1.	During the practice of Vasi yogam, the consumption of rejuvenation herbs (Kaya Karpam) Karisaalai (<i>Eclipta prostrata</i>), Neeli (<i>Indigofera indica</i>) and Vallarai (<i>Centella asiatica</i>) with milk for 48 days (1 Mandalam) is emphasized. To manipulate the Subtle breath (Vasi), various Siddhars have followed consumption of different karpams. Thirumoolar – Karisalai (<i>Eclipta prostrata</i>), Kaalangi – Karandhai (<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i>), Bogar – Omam (<i>Trachyspermum ammi</i>), Pathanjali – Serupadai (<i>Coldenia procumbens</i>), Machamuni – Vallarai (<i>Centella asiatica</i>), Koormamuni – Karuveezhi (Black variety of <i>Cadaba indica</i>)	<i>Pōkar karpam 300</i>
2.	Consumption of Karum Kaiyaan (black variety of <i>Eclipta prostrata</i>) Karpam and Meni Karpam (<i>Acalypha indica</i>) is manifested along with the practise of Vasi yogam.	<i>Taṇvantiri karukkaṭai nikaṇṭu</i>
3.	The consumption of Saathikkai Karpam (<i>Myristica fragrans</i>) is manifested during the vasi Yogam practice. The unripened fruit of <i>Myristica fragrans</i> (Saathikkai) is purified by soaking in leaf juice of <i>Cannabis sativa</i> (kanja) for 5 times and then dried. 10 Nutmegs, 21 grams of clove (5 varagan) and 21 grams of	<i>Kōrakkār cantirarēkai 200</i>

	Cardamom (5 varagan) are powdered and ground with leaf juice of <i>Cannabis sativa</i> and dried under sunlight. This is repeated for 10 times. Then each pill (Kuligai) is made in size of Milagu.	
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KAYA KARPAM HERBS CONSUMED DURING VASI YOGAM

	<p><i>Ponnangani</i> <i>Alternanthera sessilis</i></p>
	<p><i>Karisalai</i> <i>(Eclipta prostrata)</i></p>
	<p><i>Avuri</i> <i>(Indiofera tinctoria)</i></p>
	<p><i>Vallarai</i> <i>Centella asiatica</i></p>
	<p><i>Saathikkai</i> <i>Myristica fragrans</i></p>

DIETARY ADVICE

S.NO	DIET AND FOOD HABITS	LITERATURE REFERENCE
1.	Siddhar Agathiyar suggests the usage of mixture of coconut milk and grated coconut as topical application over soles to regulate the extra heat produced during Vasi yogam practice.	<i>Akattiyar caumiya cākaram 1200</i>
2.	Daily consumption of <i>Oxalis corniculata</i> (Puliyarai), <i>Alternanthera sessile</i> (Koduppai), <i>Piper nigrum</i> (Milagu) is recommended.	<i>Akattiyar vāta caumiyam 1200</i>
3.	The food has to be consumed only once in a day. Intake of rice and cow's milk rice during the practice of Vasi yogam is suggested.	<i>Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti</i>

- ❖ In *Akattiyar caumiya cākaram 1200*, Siddhar *Akattiyar* suggests to use mixture of coconut milk and grated coconut as topical application over soles to control over heat produced during Vasi yogam.

Pārunī yippaṭiyē vāciyōkam
pārkkaiyilē mavuṇamatu pilakkuñ citti
kārunī cūtukonaṭā luḷḷaṅ kālil
kalacappāl pūraṇamuṅ kalantu pūca
cērunī puliyārai koṭuppai ventu
cirappāka miḷakucār tiṇamum koḷḷu
cārunī talaimuḷuka vakaiyaik kēḷu
taṇimīḷaku amuritaṇi laraittuk kāṇē
Akattiyar caumiya cākaram 1200 verse 1194

BATH

- ❖ The paste of fruit of *Piper nigrum* (Milagu) pestled with Amuri can be used as topical application over scalp for bath.

Kāṇavē yamuritaṇil miḷaka raittuk
karuṇaiyuṭaṅ tāṅkuḷaittut talaiyil tēyttup
pēṇavē vennīrāl muḷuku maintā
peritāṇa kapālattiṅ tōṣaṅ tīrum
pūṇavē kaṇṇerivu kapālak kuttu
puttiyuṭaṅ tīrumaṭā putti yākat
tōṇavē kaṇmūṭik kaṇṇaip pāru
cuttamuṭa ṇirukaṇṇuṅ cōti kēḷē.

- *Akattiyar caumiya cākaram 1200* verse 1195

- ❖ *Tirumūlar karukkaṭai vaittiyam 600*, suggests to apply Pancha Karpam powder over scalp by mixing with cow's milk and take head bath while practicing Vasi yogam.

BENEFITS

- ❖ This Yogic rejuvenation practice daily makes our skin texture to glow like sun. By the *Akattiyar antaraṅka tīkṣā viti*, Vasi yogam paves way to eliminate 96 Thathuvams and to constrain 21,600 breath in *Cuḷumuṇai* energy channel.
- ❖ *Cuppīramaṇiyar ṅāṇam 200* prospers the importance of practicing Vasi yogam. It helps to attain stage of True consciousness and enlightenment.

“*Ventaṇalāl kaṭṭiya tōr vāciyōkam*

.....*Yōkam kaṭantōrka laṅṅē*”

- ❖ By *Kākapujaṅṅar perunūl kāviyam 1000*, Vasi yogam rejuvenation technique prevents greying of hair and extends the life span.

- ❖ *Tirumūlar karukkaṭai vaittiyam 600* states that Vasi attainment is best.

“*Vācivā venru vāciyil tāṭi*

vāciyai aṅkaṅkē vaittunī cātittāl

vāciyum īcaṇum maruviyē onrākum

vāciyaip pōl citti marṅṅum illaiyē”

- ❖ *Pulattiyar karpam 300* emphasizes the prevention of Rebirth by regular practice of Vasi yogam.

- ❖ By *Akattiyar vāta caumiyam 1200*, vasi yogam guides to attain Siva Yogam.

Pōccappā kurikāṭṭa vāciyōkam pūṭṭuvatāl civayōka muttāṅṅaccu

āccappā iṅṅūlcā karamēyākum

aṅivāṅa cākarattai yārtāṅ colvār

vāccappā purattiyāṅē vācimārkkam

makattāṅa nantiyoḷi kaṅkoḷḷātu

pēccappā piṅkalaiyil ṅnciṅkenru

pīlamāṅa ravimukamā yiruntu pare (verse 1197)

- ❖ *Pōkar karpam 300*, states practice of Vasi yogam ceases appetite, laziness and sleep. It helps to prosper with 64 siddhis.

- ❖ According to verse 102 of *Pōkar 7000*, the practice of Vasi Yogam facilitates the attainment of true consciousness. It also aids to accomplish Siva Yogam.

Veḷiyāna vāciyattāṇ varavaṭaittu

vīṭṭukkuḷ aṅkaṅkē vaittiṭṭuttāṇ taṇiyākavaiṭṭiṭṭuc cātittākkāl cātittavāciyumīcaṇum oṇṛākum

vaḷiyāka vāciyaippōl cittoṇṇumillai

mācitta civaṇavarum vāciyoṇṇil

oḷiyāka vāciyatu uyiraimiṭṭum urutiyām civayōkat tuṇmaitāṇē

- ❖ *Tēraiyaṇ civapūjā viti* suggests to Vasi Yogam to attain 64 Siddhis.
- ❖ *Rāmatēvar ṇāṇakēcari* embodies Vasi yogam as rejuvenation techniques to prevent incidence of diseases to attain Kaaya Siddhi and Attama Siddhi.

SCIENTIFIC OVERVIEW / PERCEPTION

MOLECULAR BIOLOGICAL SCIENCE OF VASI YOGAM

The Pineal gland is a highly vascularised, singular, unpaired gland, and its most well-known function is the synthesis and release of the hormone melatonin, which regulates the sleep-wake cycle as well as other bodily rhythms. Melatonin is also involved in regulating mood, and it possesses immune and neuroprotective functions, regulates neural stem cell production and is one of the most powerful and available anti-oxidants in the human body, particularly in the brain.

Pineal gland possesses a pivotal spiritual function, that it is a gateway to higher states of consciousness, and that it can be “activated” through various Yogic practices such as meditation or breathing practices. It is considered to be part of the physiological representation of the “third eye” by many people, most likely because it possesses anatomical similarities and shares phylogenetic history with the eye itself.

The pineal gland, along with the entire corpora quadragemina, had considerably higher activation during Yogic practice. Increased melatonin levels in Yogic practitioners have also been observed in several studies.

The structural integrity of the Pineal using voxel based morphometry (VBM) demonstrates morphometric differences in this melatoninergetic structure in long-term Yogic practitioners.

Respiration is a primary pneumatic driver of cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) dynamics. Yogic

breathing practices are known to modulate CSF dynamics in a pulsatile fashion which results in waste clearance in and around the pineal gland, which is directly exposed to the ventricular space. Similarly, increased CSF flow might augment distribution of melatonin which is released directly into the CSF.

In addition, increased ventricular dynamics could generate a weak piezoelectric induction in the pineal via mechanical stimulation of calcite micro-crystals which are known to be present there. A final, possibility is that the habenular activation observed during Yogic practice by (quadragemina study) induces activation of the pineal gland via a previously observed direct efferent pathway from the medial habenula to the pineal. Melatonin can regulate the glial response and reduce damage to neural cells resulting from oxidative stress and inflammation.

ANTIOXIDANT

Antioxidants are a broad class of compounds and enzymes that neutralize excessive reactive oxygen molecules derived from metabolic processes and prevent ensuing tissue damage. Melatonin is an extremely powerful antioxidant, particularly in the brain. Minimising age-related decline in melatonin production via a Yogic practice could have the potential to lower oxidative stress in the brain early-on in disease progression and affect the time-course of both age-related and pathological neural decline.

STEM CELLS & NEURAL REGENERATION

Melatonin regulates neural differentiation of induced pluripotent stem cells via melatonin receptor activation. Maintaining melatonin production and release at adequate levels is therefore desirable for neurogenesis and neural plasticity, and a regular Yogic practice could assist in achieving this by both increasing baseline melatonin levels and maintaining or increasing pineal integrity.

Yogic Breathing practice could be beneficial in the context of cognitive and neurophysiological ageing by improving melatonin availability and regulation. Given melatonin's downstream roles in sleep, free radical scavenging, anti-inflammation, immune modulation and neural stem cell proliferation and differentiation, it seems plausible that early pineal degeneration could play a causal role in age-related brain degeneration, and that structural preservation via Yogic practice could be beneficial.

Yogic practice supports cognitive functions including attention and interoceptive processing and is associated with structural changes across cortical networks including prefrontal regions, and the insula. The Pineal Gland, a key producer of melatonin, which regulates circadian rhythms that augment sleep-wake patterns, and may also provide neuroprotective benefits to offset cognitive decline. Increased melatonin levels as well as increased fMRI BOLD signal in the Pineal Gland has been observed as benefit of Yogic practice.

The potential mechanisms by which Yogic practice influences Pineal Gland function, hormonal metabolism, and Grey Matter maintenance include melatonin's roles in sleep, immune response, inflammation modulation and stem cell and neural regeneration.

Both circadian rhythm and Vasi Yogam are related to physiological processes and the regulation of life energy. Circadian Rhythm is a biological process governed by molecular clocks in humans that operates on a 24-hour cycle. It is driven by the master clock in the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCN) of the brain, which synchronizes bodily functions which operates through genetic feedback loops, involving clock genes and proteins such as CLOCK, BMAL1, PER, and CRY.

Manipulating Ultradian rhythm of Respiration involves regulation of breath to slower the rate of respiration and extend the life span.

METAPHYSICAL PERCEPTION OF VASI YOGAM

The body-mind's central regulating system is called the subtle body. The subtle pranic energy has been scientifically recognized and defined as a biofield. It provides the scientific foundation for a holistic view of life and techniques for integrative medicine. Its effects can be observed and quantified through various physiological, psychological and cellular responses. Medical physiology, cell biology, and biophysics provide the scientific framework within which evidence for biofields, their proposed receptors, and functions is presented.

The subtle body is composed of the coordinated development of four basic elements. The structural elements include energy channels (Naadi) and energy plexes (Aadharam). The functional elements are vital energy or winds (Vasi) and metabolic thermal energy (Agni). Mental and physical elements interact through bimodal causation at the interface of mind states with energy patterns. In top-down causation, mental processes direct the dynamic flow of energies and drops and, with repetitive flow, these in turn alter the structure of energy channels and energy plexes.

The coarse level of the subtle body consists of an extensive network of peripheral channels that branch out in complex circuits from energy plexes (Aadharam) along the central channel. These peripheral channels support gross sensorimotor and physiological processes, such as the functioning of the external senses, proprioception, locomotion, and the internal organs of the cardiorespiratory, metabolic, immunologic and genitourinary systems. This network, aligned with waking-state consciousness, is structured with a number of primary channels that issue directly from the central channel at one of physio psychic centers along the neuraxis.

The extremely subtle level of the subtle body is nested within the central channel and constitutes the biomolecular source and regulatory center of the 10 primary energies (Vaayus) that operate within all of its channels, energy plexes, and networks. Within this framework, the six types of contemplative practice are mapped onto different levels and regions of the subtle body, reinforcing integrative structures and self-regulating functions throughout. Specifically, the more advanced the practice, the deeper it moves toward the extremely subtle core level of the subtle body and the further down the rostral–caudal axis of the central channel.

DISCUSSION

The current study deals with the exploration of fundamentals and principles of Vasi Yogam in accordance with broad spectrum view by various Siddhars. This documentation endows comprehensible elaboration about the synonyms, definition, procedure, time, duration, significance of Vasi Yogam and Scientific perception with molecular biological Science and Meta physical theory of subtle body. Interpretations of Vasi yogam methodology from classical literatures of Siddhars including Agathiyar, Bogar, Thirumoolar, Kaagabujandar, Siva vakiyar, Pulathiyar, Rama devar, Korakkar, Kalanginathar, Theraiyar, Dhanwanthiri and Machamuni have been accomplished. About 40 Siddha treatises have acquainted the essence

of this Yogic Karpam technique. A profound elucidation on attaining enlightenment through this yogic practice and its mechanism as Yoga karpam has been furnished. An insight into proficient doctrine about functioning of subtle body through manipulation of subtle breath (Vasi) across energy channels of body is inferred.

CONCLUSION

Through this extensive literature review, the enthralling erudition of our Siddhar on Vasi Yogam and Yogic rejuvenation concept to attain enlightenment is explicated. This study enables to ascertain the subtle body principles and working mechanism in the procedure of perceiving true consciousness. Multifacet approach on Vasi yogam by various Siddhars is accomplished prospering the eminence of Siddhar Yoga Maruthuvam. Further extensive research on Vasi Yogam might be carried out based on documentation and interpretation of Kirlian photography of Vasi Yogam practice.

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